

Synthesis of N¹-(β-cyanoethyl)-2-heterocyclic-(p-arylidene)-aminobenzenesulphonamides and Their Insecticidal Activity

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Various substituted cyanoethylated sulphonamides were prepared and screened for their insecticidal activity. They showed excellent insecticidal activity on male and female cockroaches.

A large number of cyanoethylated sulphonamides are known to possess insecticidal activity¹⁻³. Kretov *et al*⁴ have reported the cyanoethylation of sulphanilamide and sulphapyridine. In continuation of our earlier interest in incorporating a cyanoethyl group in substituted sulphonamides⁵, capable of exhibiting insecticidal activity, it was thought to synthesize N¹-(β-cyanoethyl)-2-heterocyclic-(p-arylidene)aminobenzenesulphonamides. Subsequently these sulphonamides were converted into amines and tetrazoles which exhibited antibacterial and anti-inflammatory activity^{6,7}. The present communication describes the synthesis and insecticidal activity of N¹-(β-cyanoethyl)-2-heterocyclic-(p-arylidene)aminobenzenesulphonamides.

The i.r. spectra of the compounds showed absorption in the range of 2215 to 2260 cm⁻¹ due to -C≡N stretching vibration. The respective asymmetric and symmetric stretching modes of vibration of S=O appeared in the range of 1330 to 1380 cm⁻¹ and 1150 to 1180 cm⁻¹. The compounds also showed absorption band in the range of 1615 to 1640 cm⁻¹ due to >C=N- stretching vibration.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The i.r. spectra were taken on Perkin-Elmer 137 and 177 spectrophotometers.

The Schiff's bases of N¹-2-heterocyclicsulphanilamides were prepared by the condensation of different substituted sulphanilamides with aryl aldehydes⁸⁻¹⁰.

Synthesis of N¹-(β-cyanoethyl)-2-heterocyclic-(p-arylidene)aminobenzenesulphonamide [1-24] :

To a well stirred solution containing N¹-2-heterocyclic-(p-arylidene)aminobenzenesulphonamide (0.01 mole), pyridine (20 ml) and 'Triton B' (1 g) was added dropwise acrylonitrile (0.01 mole) at 30-35°. The mixture was stirred for 35 to 48 hours

at room temperature. It was acidified and poured into ice water. The solid mass was obtained which was crystallized from alcohol. The results are cited in Table 1.

TABLE 1—N¹-(β-CYANOETHYL)-2-HETEROCYCLIC-(p-ARYLIDENE) AMINO BENZENESULPHONAMIDES

Sl. No.	R ₁	Yield %	m.p. °C	Mean K.D. time (hr) % concentration	
				0.5	0.1
R = Pyrimidyl					
1.	H	60.00	220	8.0	10.5
2.	p-OH	75.00	210	7.0	9.5
3.	o-OH	70.00	235	6.5	8.0
4.	p-Cl	66.50	242	6.0	7.0
5.	p-(CH ₃) ₂ N	58.00	200	7.0	8.5
6.	p-CH ₃ CONH	72.00	250	9.0	11.5
R = 4-Methyl pyrimidyl					
7.	H	75.00	150	7.0	10.5
8.	p-OH	75.00	228	6.5	9.0
9.	o-OH	73.00	242	7.0	8.5
10.	p-Cl	73.00	225	5.0	6.5
11.	p-(CH ₃) ₂ N	77.00	230	7.5	10.0
12.	p-CH ₃ CONH	78.00	240	8.0	9.5
R = 4,6-Dimethyl pyrimidyl					
13.	H	66.66	195	8.0	11.5
14.	p-OH	70.20	243	7.5	10.5
15.	o-OH	61.50	265	6.5	10.0
16.	p-Cl	71.40	242	6.0	9.5
17.	p-(CH ₃) ₂ N	74.00	180	9.0	12.0
18.	p-CH ₃ CONH	77.00	208	10.0	14.0
R = Thiazolyl					
19.	H	72.00	220	9.5	12.0
20.	p-OH	72.70	150	8.5	10.5
21.	o-OH	69.20	168	7.5	10.0
22.	p-Cl	80.40	228	7.0	9.0
23.	p-(CH ₃) ₂ N	70.00	265	9.0	14.0
24.	p-CH ₃ CONH	78.00	200	11.0	12.0
Standard Insecticide Parathion				4	5.5
Solvent Acetone				40	40

Insecticidal Activity : The compounds listed in Table I were screened for their insecticidal activity on male and female cockroaches by the method of Nash¹¹. Acetone solutions of the compounds were applied at a dosage of 0.02 ml of .5% and .1% concentrations. Parathion, a standard insecticide, was used for control.

The data in table show that all compounds have insecticidal activity. Maximum insecticidal activity was observed in compound No. 10 and minimum in compound No. 18. It indicates that substitution of *p*-Cl group in arylidene moiety increased the insecticidal activity. A definite-structure activity relationship could not be established from the results obtained.

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